

Development & Assessment of Assays Capable of Data Generation for Training and Benchmarking Models for PET Hydrolase Engineering

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Abstract

Machine learning and computational approaches are rapidly transforming protein design and engineering, yet their broader impact remains constrained by a critical bottleneck: the scarcity of high-quality, large-scale experimental datasets on industrially relevant properties such as catalytic activity and soluble expression. Using PET hydrolase, an enzyme of significant industrial and environmental relevance for enzymatic plastic degradation, we systematically developed and evaluated three independent assay platforms against key criteria of data quality, scalability, and industrial relevance. Our report shows that in these pilot experiments, only one out of the three platforms generated consistent high quality data sufficient for training and benchmarking models. This work offers practical insights for the field as it scales towards larger and more ambitious data-driven protein engineering campaigns.

Introduction

Machine learning (ML) is rapidly accelerating protein engineering, enabling powerful approaches for predicting, designing, and optimizing proteins across applications ranging from therapeutics to industrial enzymes^{1,2}. Progress has been especially visible in protein design, where diffusion models, protein language models, and other computational approaches have enabled the design of many proteins with tailored properties³⁻⁸. These advances depend not only on algorithm innovations, but also the datasets used to train and evaluate these methods.

Recent efforts to curate these datasets have emerged. For example, FLIP and ProteinGym provide standardized benchmarks on protein fitness, while MaveDB curates large-scale variant-effect measurements⁹⁻¹¹. More recently, enzyme-focused efforts such as CARE and EnzEngDB organize enzyme-function sequence-function datasets^{12,13}. Yet for many target

functions, the curated data needed to train and benchmark such models are sparse or do not exist, making experimental data generation a central bottleneck for the field.

This bottleneck is especially acute for enzyme engineering. Enzyme optimization requires quantitative measurements of properties inherently context-dependent– for example, catalytic activity on target substrates under process-relevant conditions, substrate specificity, thermostability, or soluble expression in production-relevant hosts^{14–16}. Generating these datasets is difficult because assay platforms often force tradeoffs between throughput, measurement fidelity, and relevance to the intended engineering objective¹⁷. An additional challenge therefore lies in identifying experimental platforms and assay conditions that yield reliable, accurate, and relevant measurements at scale.

In this work, we chose to focus on PET hydrolases (PETases) as a case study for industrial enzyme dataset generation. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) is a widely used thermoplastic polymer whose inefficient recycling contributes to environmental accumulation and continued dependence on fossil-derived material. PET hydrolases, enzymes that depolymerize PET into reusable monomers, offer a route to closed-loop recycling, but industrial deployment requires improved activity under process conditions (e.g., elevated temperature, low pH) along with cost-effective soluble expression. PET hydrolase engineering demands exactly the kind of datasets that are difficult to generate: quantitative, scalable, and grounded in industrially-relevant properties^{18–21}.

We developed and assessed three independent assay platforms for generating labeled datasets for PET hydrolase activity and soluble expression: a cell-free expression and PET film degradation assay with a Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy (UV-vis) readout; an *E. coli* expression platform coupled to rapid-fire mass spectrometry for activity measurements on PET suspensions; and a microfluidic droplet-based cell-free expression and activity assay using fluorescence and next-generation sequencing-based enrichment readouts. Using a reference panel of 20 PET hydrolases, we generated data from each platform and reported the reproducibility and data quality encountered across activity and expression readouts. Only one of the three platforms produced consistently high-quality data suitable for model benchmarking in our pilot experiments, highlighting the importance of rigorous assay validation before scaling experimental data generation.

Results & Discussion

We developed three independent assays for measuring PETase expression and activity under different temperature, and pH conditions: 1) Cell free expression & PET film degradation (Figure 1A–B) 2) *E. coli* expression & rapid-fire mass spectrometry (RFMS) (Figure 2A–B) and 3) Microfluidic cell-free expression and activity (Figure 3A–B). Together, the three assay platforms allow different degrees of scalability and relevance to real-world application. For all assay development methods, we selected a set of 20 previously published naturally occurring or engineered PETases (hereafter referred to as the ‘reference PETases’) (Table 1, Supplementary

File S1)²²⁻²⁶. These enzymes were selected to span a range of expression and activity levels to enable evaluation of the sensitivity and dynamic range of each assay. In addition, this panel of enzymes served as calibration standards for assay benchmarking. All data quality assessments presented here were deduced from the pilot-scale experiments performed using these reference PETases (Table 2).

Table 1: Reference PETases

Enzyme ID	Genebank Accession
LCC PETase	AEV21261.1
IsPETase	WP_054022242.1
Mipa PETase	WP_091558835.1
Kubu PETase	WP_116180173.1
Cut190	WP_015787089.1
CaPETase	SHM40309.1
WP_020639922.1	WP_020639922.1
WP_117215036.1	WP_117215036.1
SM14Est	WP_103503499.1
WP_083947829.1	WP_083947829.1
PC5	WP_075975245.1
Est2	BAK48590.1
WP_078759821.1	WP_078759821.1
LCC PETase ICCG	N/A Engineered
Mipa PETase M19	N/A Engineered
Kubu PETase M12	N/A Engineered
FAST PETase	N/A Engineered
CaPETase M9	N/A Engineered
HotPETase	N/A Engineered
dMipa PETase (-tive ctrl)	N/A Engineered

Table 2: Assessment of assay platforms

Feature	Platform 1: Cell-free + PET film (UV-vis)	Platform 2: <i>E. coli</i> + RFMS	Platform 3: Microfluidic droplet assay
Expression system	Cell-free (<i>E. coli</i> extract)	<i>E. coli</i> (<i>in vivo</i> expression)	Cell-free (droplet-based)
Substrate	3D-printed PET films (tunable crystallinity)	PET powder/suspension	PET nanoparticles + fluorogenic substrate
Activity Readout	End-point UV-vis	Rapid-fire mass spectrometry (RFMS)	Relative NGS read-counts after microfluidic droplet sorting
Expression Readout	Split-GFP	A660 after Ni-NTA purification	Fluorescent protein-binding dye + NGS enrichment
Throughput	High (10^3 scale)	High (10^3 scale)	Very high (10^4 - 10^6 scale potential)
Data quality (Expression)	Not reported	Low (Mean CV = 27%)	Low quality (poor correlation to ground truth; $R^2 \leq 0.34$)
Data quality* (Activity)	High (Mean CV = 11.5%)	Low (Mean CV = 49%)	
Industrial Relevance	High (Activity); Low (Expression)	Moderate (Expression, Activity)	Low (Expression, Activity)
Key Strengths	Best signal-to-noise; realistic substrate; robust benchmarking data	Large-scale data generation; relevant host system	Massive scale; pooled library screening
Key limitations	Limited scalability of cell-free system	High experimental noise may limit ML utility	Poor quantitative accuracy; pipeline immaturity
Suitability for ML benchmarking	High	Low (requires substantial assay development)	Low (requires substantial assay development)

Platform 1: Cell-free expression and UV-Vis PET film degradation assay

The first platform quantifies protein expression in an *E. coli* cell-free system²⁷ using a split-green fluorescent protein (GFP)²⁸ readout and measures enzymatic activity via an endpoint UV-vis assay that tracks hydrolysis of 3D-printed PET films in microtiter plates (Figure 1A-B). To assess soluble expression, we quantified crude expression of 20 reference PETases using the split-GFP assay. Expression levels ranged from 2.6 to 26.7 μM , with 2.5 μM representing the lower limit of detection. Several PETases exceeded the expression level of the positive control *E. coli* dihydrofolate reductase (EcDHFR), indicating generally robust expression across the panel. In

contrast, MiPa PETase and Kubu PETase mutants were below the detection limit, while Cut190, LCC^{ICCG} PETase, and HOT PETase showed the highest expression (Figure 1C). Following purification with Strep-Tactin[®]-functionalized magnetic beads, all reference PETases were recovered in sufficient yield for downstream quantification (Figure S2).

To establish conditions for the endpoint activity assay, we first performed time-course measurements of PET film hydrolysis across four conditions (37 °C at pH 9.0; 37 °C at pH 5.5; 60 °C at pH 9.0; 60 °C at pH 5.5) (Figure S1, Supplementary File S3). An incubation time of 24 hours was selected as optimal, capturing both high- and low-activity enzymes. These conditions were then applied in a pilot-scale endpoint activity assay for all reference PETases (Figure 1D–G). Enzymatic activity was quantified by converting the change in absorbance at 260 nm (ΔA_{260}) into micromoles of mono-(2-hydroxy) terephthalic acid (MHET) equivalents using a standard curve (Figure 1H, Supplementary File S4). For highly active enzymes exceeding the assay's upper detection limit, samples were diluted to bring absorbance values within the linear range, and activities were corrected for the dilution factor, thereby extending the assay's dynamic range (Figure S2).

This platform demonstrated high data quality, with low variability, with a coefficient of variability (CV) of 11.5% and a broad dynamic range spanning four orders of magnitude (0–14,000 μ M MHET equivalents) (Figure 1H, Supplementary File S4). When automated, the assay can scale to thousands of samples. However, a key limitation is that the cell-free system based on minimal *E. coli* expression machinery does not capture in vivo soluble expression, which more directly correlates with industrial fermentation yields. While laboratory- and pilot-scale systems like cell-free systems, and *E. coli* are accessible and able to produce large-scale data, data generation in industrial hosts such as Bacillus or Aspergillus has only recently become experimentally tractable for contract research organizations and academic institutions¹⁶. Indeed, datasets in such hosts, obtained from industrial studies, have been reported for training and benchmarking models on soluble expression¹⁵.

Platform 2: *E. coli* expression and rapid-fire mass spectrometry (RFMS) assay

The second platform expresses PETases in *E. coli*, quantifies protein yield following Ni-NTA affinity purification using a colorimetric protein assay utilizing the Pierce 660 reagent (A660), and measures enzymatic activity on PET suspensions using RFMS (Figure 2A–B). Protein amount was quantified after purification using the A660 assay (Figure 2C, Supplementary File S5), yielding an average titer of 0.076 mg/mL from 1 mL cultures. However, the assay exhibited substantial variability, with an average CV of 27%. This variability arose both from the A660 assay itself and from fluctuations in culture growth, as reflected in variability in final optical density (OD) prior to harvest (Figure S3, Supplementary File S5).

To establish a high-throughput (HTP) activity assay across pH and temperature conditions, we first expressed and purified 10 reference PETases at large scale to >90% purity using affinity chromatography followed by size exclusion chromatography. These purified enzymes were used

to develop and optimize an RFMS-based assay for measuring hydrolytic activity on solid PET powder under both low- and high-pH conditions (Figure 2D, Supplementary File S5). This protocol was then applied in a pilot-scale experiment using 20 reference constructs purified via a one-step HTP affinity workflow (Figure 2E, Supplementary File S5). The resulting activity measurements showed high variability, with an average CV of 49%.

Given the platform's scalability, we expanded the assay to generate larger datasets. We selected pH 5.5 at 25 °C as a low-pH condition due to the relative lack of highly efficient PETases under these conditions²⁹. We then cloned, expressed, and assayed a random subset of 310 uncharacterized PETase genes identified from genomic and metagenomic sources²² (Supplementary Files S6 and S16), along with site-saturation variant libraries (SSVLs) for three enzymes (CaPETase, WP_117215036.1, and SM13Est; Supplementary Files S7–S9). As expected, the expression assay exhibited substantial variability, as indicated by the CV of the positive control (CaPETase M9). For activity measurements of natural homologs, the positive control generally showed CV values below 30% (Supplementary Files S6–S9). In contrast, experiments involving SSVL libraries displayed significantly higher CVs, indicating increased noise in these datasets.

Overall, this platform enables data generation at the scale of thousands of samples per experiment but suffers from high variability in both expression and activity measurements. Contributing factors likely include heterogeneity in PET powder crystallinity and variability inherent to *E. coli* expression systems, which, while widely used, may not represent the most optimal industrial production hosts (e.g., *Bacillus* or *Aspergillus*)¹⁶. Notably, similar assay formats have been successfully used for large-scale data generation in prior studies³⁰. Thus, the limitations observed here likely reflect the need for further assay optimization rather than fundamental constraints of the platform itself.

Platform 3: Microfluidic based cell-free expression and activity assay

The third platform employs fluorescence-activated droplet sorting (FADS)³¹, a microfluidic approach in which PETase libraries are expressed within droplets. Protein expression is quantified using a fluorogenic protein-binding dye, while enzymatic activity is measured via fluorescence generated by the unquenching of fluorescein dibenzoate released upon PET nanoparticle degradation by active PETases (Figure 3A–B).

To obtain quantitative estimates of expression and activity, droplets containing an *in vitro* expressed PETase library were sorted into low-, medium-, and high-fluorescence bins. Variant enrichment in each bin was calculated relative to the presorted library. These enrichment values were then calibrated with gold-standard low-throughput (LTP) measurements—protein expression quantified using a fluorogenic Qubit assay and activity measured by LC–MS—to estimate expression (mg/mL) and specific activity (nmol·s⁻¹·g⁻¹) in standard units (Supplementary File S10).

For benchmarking, activity was evaluated under two conditions: 25 °C and 55 °C at pH 9.0. Expression and activity of individual library members were independently measured using Qubit quantification and LC-MS, respectively. These LTP measurements were used to calibrate the enrichment-based estimates from the FADS assay. Comparison of estimated versus gold-standard values revealed weak overall correlation, with the best performance observed for activity at 55 °C ($R^2 = 0.34$) (Figure 3C-E).

Given that the primary advantage of the microfluidic platform is its scalability, we next evaluated its performance on full variant libraries. Activity assays were conducted at 25 °C and 55 °C (pH 9.0) using SSVs of two enzymes (CaPETase and SM14Est). Unexpectedly, sorted populations showed substantial enrichment of multi-mutant sequences, despite the input libraries being predominantly composed of wild-type (WT) and single mutants (Figure S4, Supplementary File S12). For example, in the assay for CaPETase at 55 °C, initial plasmid sequencing indicated 9% WT, 84% single mutants, and 7% double mutants. However, following amplification and sorting, the population became dominated by higher-order variants, including newly observed triple mutants, with 96% of sequences classified in the high-fluorescence bin (Figure S4). Correspondingly, single mutants present in the initial library were underrepresented relative to these higher-order variants (Supplementary Files S11-S13). The emergence and enrichment of unintended mutations during library amplification and sorting suggest protocol-induced errors or biases, resulting in inconsistently labeled data. Consequently, despite its high throughput, this platform currently produces unreliable measurements for downstream analysis due to a combination of poorly developed assay platform, and a mutagenic protocol that introduces unintended mutations.

Overall, the microfluidic platform did not generate reliable quantitative data in its current implementation. In the pilot-scale experiments, sorting-based estimates showed poor agreement with low-throughput reference measurements, indicating limited quantitative accuracy. In the full-scale library experiments, the workflow introduced unintended higher-order mutations during amplification and sorting, making it difficult to assign fluorescence enrichment to the intended input variants. Although microfluidic droplet assays have been used for high-throughput enzyme screening, generating quantitative labeled datasets for model training remains challenging³². The platform also has limited ability to assess activity on crystalline PET because it uses amorphous PET nanoparticles rather than bulk crystalline substrates. Finally, because expression is performed in a cell-free system, the assay does not directly measure soluble expression yields in fermentative production hosts.

Conclusion

For ML-driven enzyme engineering, assay platforms are not merely experimental tools; they define the quality of the datasets on which models are trained and evaluated. Here, we used PET hydrolases as a test case to assess three independent platforms for measuring enzyme activity and soluble expression. We compared these platforms across reproducibility, quantitative

accuracy, scalability, and alignment with the intended engineering objective to determine their suitability for generating machine-learning-ready enzyme datasets.

The comparison revealed distinct strengths and limitations across the three assays. The cell-free expression and PET film degradation platform produced the highest-quality activity data, with strong reproducibility and a broad dynamic range, making it the most suitable of the three platforms for model benchmarking in our pilot experiments. However, its use of a cell-free expression system limits its ability to report directly on soluble expression in fermentative production hosts. The *E. coli* expression and RFMS platform offered a more scalable route to data generation and a more conventional expression context, but both expression and activity measurements showed high variability, indicating that further assay optimization would be required before such data could be used confidently for model development. The microfluidic droplet platform offered the greatest potential throughput, but in its current implementation showed poor agreement with low-throughput reference measurements and introduced unintended sequence artifacts during scale-up, limiting confidence in the resulting dataset.

These results provide a targeted roadmap for improving the two higher-throughput platforms. For the *E. coli* expression and RFMS platform, future work should first decompose the major sources of variability across the workflow, prioritizing culture growth, purification and protein quantification, PET substrate handling, RFMS measurement, and plate or replicate effects. Once the dominant sources of noise are identified, the platform could be improved through tighter process controls, stronger normalization strategies, targeted replicate designs, and orthogonal validation against a higher-fidelity reference assay before scaling to larger libraries. For the microfluidic droplet platform, the most urgent priority is establishing genotype measurement fidelity throughout the workflow. This could include sequence-integrity checkpoints after library construction, amplification, encapsulation, and sorting, along with spike-in controls of known activity and expression to monitor enrichment accuracy. Improved calibration against low-throughput reference measurements and predefined quality-control thresholds would also be needed before using this platform to generate quantitative datasets for model training.

Our results highlight specific challenges for PETases, underscoring key tradeoffs between throughput, fidelity for end-use properties (e.g., degradation conditions, substrate, fermentative host) and expected data quality. While the learnings here are specific to PETases, they can be generally applicable to many other enzymes. Future efforts focused on cost-effective, high-quality, and accurate measurements will be instrumental in training and benchmarking the next generation of models. With continued investment in assay standardization and scalability, the field is becoming well-positioned to generate the reliable, quantitative datasets needed to accelerate machine learning-driven enzyme engineering.

Methods

Platform 1: Cell-free expression and PET film degradation assay platform

Construct Design and Assembly

To enable rapid quantification and affinity purification of PETase variants, the original C-terminal His-tag was replaced with a multifunctional tag consisting of Linker-GFP11-Linker-Twin-Strep-tag II (TSTII)³³. The GFP11 peptide enables fluorescence-based quantification via split-GFP complementation, while the Twin-Strep-tag II allows high-affinity purification using Strep-Tactin[®]XT resin.

The tagging cassette was incorporated using a two-step PCR strategy:

Adapter insertion (PCR 1): Adapter sequences required for tag integration were introduced through PCR amplification of the PETase constructs. Either purified plasmid DNA or crude lysate from glycerol stocks was used as the template source. This step generated amplicons containing overlap regions compatible with the downstream tagging cassette.

Tag integration (PCR 2): The full Linker-GFP11-Linker-TSTII framework was introduced using Overlap Extension PCR (OE-PCR). During this step, the adapter-containing PETase amplicon and the tagging cassette were fused via overlapping homology regions, generating the final tagged constructs suitable for cell-free expression.

Enzyme Expression and Purification

PETase variants were expressed using an *E. coli*-based cell-free protein synthesis system using a 100 μ L expression batch. Reactions were supplemented with the disulfide bond isomerase DsbC and oxidized glutathione (GSSG) to promote correct disulfide bond formation and enhance folding of secreted enzyme variants. Cell-free reactions were incubated at 25 °C for 14 hours. For the PET degradation assay, proteins were purified using magnetic Strep-Tactin[®]XT affinity beads, exploiting the C-terminal Twin-Strep-II tag. Purification was performed to remove background components from the cell-free mixture that could interfere with UV-based detection of PET degradation products.

Protein Yield Quantification

Soluble enzyme concentration in the crude cell-free reaction mixture was determined using a split-fluorescent protein quantification system. In this approach, the expressed GFP11-tagged proteins were complemented with GFP1-10 to reconstitute a fluorescent GFP complex, allowing quantification through fluorescence measurement. After affinity purification, protein concentrations were determined using a fluorescent protein-binding dye, enabling accurate quantification of purified enzyme preparations.

PET Degradation Assay

PET hydrolytic activity was evaluated by measuring the release of aromatic degradation products from PET substrates using the purified enzyme at a reaction volume of 150 μL at 37 °C or 60 °C, shaking at 800 rpm and incubated for 15 hours.

Substrate Preparation

The PET substrate consisted of 3D-printed virgin PET material. Prior to use, the substrate was pre-treated with 1 M NaOH for 1 hour, followed by washing, to increase surface accessibility and enhance enzymatic hydrolysis. For high pH 50 mM glycine-NaOH, 50 mM NaCl, pH 9.0, supplemented with 10% (v/v) DMSO was used, and for low pH 50 mM citrate buffer, pH 5.5, supplemented with 10% (v/v) DMSO was used. DMSO was included to improve the solubility of hydrophobic PET degradation products while remaining within a concentration range compatible with enzyme activity.

Activity Measurement

Product formation was monitored by measuring absorbance at 260 nm, corresponding to aromatic PET hydrolysis products such as terephthalic acid derivatives.

A purified cell-free blank was measured in parallel to account for background absorbance originating from the expression system or purification process. Samples exceeding the linear detection range after the 15-hour reaction were re-measured following a 10-fold dilution, and reported values were corrected for the dilution factor. To ensure spectral consistency and confirm the presence of aromatic degradation products, full absorbance spectra (220–330 nm) were also recorded and evaluated for each reaction.

Conversion of endpoint measurements to MHET product equivalents

When PET is enzymatically hydrolysed, the primary soluble product released is MHET (mono(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid), an aromatic mono-ester that absorbs UV light at 260 nm. Product release was quantified by measuring the change in absorbance at 260 nm (ΔA_{260}) between a t_0 baseline read (before incubation) and the endpoint read (after 37 hours). The ΔA_{260} was then converted to MHET-equivalent μM using a calibration curve generated from a purified MHET standard ($y = 0.000798x + 0.081$, where $x = \mu\text{M}$ MHET and $y = \text{absorbance}$). The linear detection range of the plate reader extends to approximately 1.8 AU; samples exceeding this value were re-measured after a 10-fold dilution to bring them within the quantifiable range, and the back-calculated undiluted values are reported. The lower limit of quantification (LOQ) from the calibration curve was determined to be 35 μM MHET.

Higher MHET-equivalent μM values indicate greater PET-degrading activity: the enzyme cleaved more ester bonds in the PET substrate, releasing more aromatic product into solution. Because all reactions contained the same amount of PET substrate and were normalised to the same enzyme concentration, the reported MHET values enable direct comparison of relative catalytic performance across variants.

Platform 2: *E. coli* Expression and RFMS assay

Construct Design and Assembly

Golden gate assembly was used to clone DNA encoding CDS of each PETase sequence into PET28a (KanR) plasmid in the insert region as annotated in this genebank file. The sequence was verified using whole plasmid sequencing (Quintara Biosciences).

Large-Scale Expression & Purification of 10 Reference PETases

BL21(DE3) cells harboring plasmid DNA with each ORF were pre-cultured in 1 mL LB (Teknova) containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin and 0.5% glucose overnight at 37 °C with shaking at 300 rpm in a 96-deep well block. The next day, cells per construct were sub-cultured in 4 L of TB medium (Teknova) containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin, were grown at 37 °C while shaking at 300 rpm until mid-log phase (approximately 2-3 hours, OD 0.6-0.8), induced with 0.5 mM IPTG. Post-induction, the growth temperature was lowered to 18 °C overnight. Cells were harvested by centrifugation at 4,000 x g and pellets were frozen at -80 °C before use.

Harvested cell pellets were incubated for one hour with gentle shaking at room temperature with lysis buffer (20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, 1 U/mL Benzonase, PI tablets, and 0.1 mg/mL lysozyme) and lysates are clarified by centrifugation at 4,000 x g for 15 min at 4 °C. Protein were purified to >90% purity using affinity (Ni-NTA) followed by size exclusion chromatography.

HTP Expression

BL21(DE3) cells harboring plasmid DNA with each ORF were pre-cultured in 1 mL LB (Teknova) containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin and 0.5% glucose overnight at 37 °C with shaking at 300 rpm in a 96-deep well block. The next day, 15 µL of cells per construct were sub-cultured in 1 mL of TB medium (Teknova) containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin, were grown at 37 °C while shaking at 300 rpm until mid-log phase (approximately 2-3 hours, OD 0.6-0.8), induced with 0.5 mM IPTG. Post-induction, the growth temperature was lowered to 18 °C overnight. Cells were harvested by centrifugation at 4,000 x g and pellets were frozen at -80 °C before use.

HTP Purification

Harvested cell pellets were incubated for one hour with gentle shaking at room temperature with 1 mL of lysis buffer (20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, 1 U/mL Benzonase, PI tablets, and 0.1 mg/mL lysozyme) and lysates are clarified by centrifugation at 4,000 x g for 15 min at 4 °C. For small-scale purification, 1 mL of soluble lysate was used for IMAC pulldown with KingFisher APEX. Magnetic resin (50 µL) was washed 3 x 1 mL with 20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, and 20 mM imidazole, and then protein was eluted in 100 µL of 20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, and 300 mM imidazole. Protein concentration of purified proteins was determined by the average of two replicates in an A660 assay (Pierce) using a BSA standard curve ranging from 50-2,000 µg/mL, and was measured spectrophotometrically on a BMG LabTech SPECTROstar Nano.

Specific Activity

Purified protein in the storage buffer containing 20 mM sodium phosphate pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, and 300 mM imidazole was placed on wet ice until completely thawed. 4 µL of purified protein was added to a 96 well Costar v-bottom plate containing 196 µL of 5mg/mL powdered

PET substrate (Goodfellow ES30-PD-000132) was resuspended in either 50mM Citrate buffer pH 5.5 at 30 °C (Condition 1) or 50 mM Glycine buffer pH 9.0 at 30 °C (Condition 2) using a Perkin-Elmer Janus Mini pipetting station. Plates were sealed and shaken at 450rpm within a temperature-controlled plate shaker (Allsheng Thermo Shaker) at 30 °C for two, six, and eight hours. Reaction was stopped by incubating on wet ice for 5 minutes followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes at 4 °C to pellet the PET substrate. 50 µL of supernatant was transferred to a 96 well Costar v-bottom plate containing 100 µL of crash solution (0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile) containing 300 µM d4-TPA (internal mass spectroscopy standard). Plates were sealed with pierceable plate seal and shaken at 450 rpm at room temperature for 5 minutes followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes at room temperature. The enzyme product was then determined using an Applied Biosystems RapidFire/ Sciex 4000 QQQ Mass Spectrometer. A 10 µL sample of each well was injected into the mass spectrometer and the peak areas of TPA, MHET and the internal standard was determined. Included with each plate of samples was a blank, negative and positive control. Additionally, a standard curve of TPA and MHET was included with each set of plates. Samples were tested in duplicate. Peak areas were normalized using the internal standard d4-TPA to correct for any differences incurred during sampling. Normalized peak area for each product was interpolated from a standard curve of TPA and MHET to determine the molar equivalent generated of the enzyme product. Products generated at each time point were analyzed by linear regression to calculate a reaction rate. The amount of protein in each sample (previously determined using a standard BCA assay) and the calculated reaction rate were used to determine the specific activity in µmoles product/min/mg enzyme.

Platform 3: Microfluidic based cell-free expression and activity assay

Expression of PETases via in vitro protein synthesis in bulk

In vitro expression of PETases was carried out using PURExpress® In Vitro Protein Synthesis Kit (New England Biolabs #E6800) and PURExpress® Disulfide Bond Enhancer (New England Biolabs #E6820) following the manufacturer's instructions. A pUC-derived plasmid containing a PETase gene was used to set up a 25-µL PURExpress reaction with a final concentration of 10 ng/µL of DNA in a 0.3-mL PCR tube. Disulfide bond enhancer reagents were added to promote adequate expression. The reaction was incubated at 37 °C for 4 hours.

If purification was required, the final reaction was diluted to 100 µL in 10 mM magnesium acetate. The resulting dilution was added to a Amicon® ultra centrifugal filter 100 kDa MWCO (Millipore #UFC510024) and high molecular weight components were removed by centrifugation at 15,000 × g and 4 °C for 30 minutes. The flowthrough was collected and used to resuspend 0.25 volumes of HisPur™ Ni-NTA resin (Thermo Scientific #88221). The His-tagged components from the PURExpress kit were let to bind the resin by mixing at 4 °C for 45 minutes. The mixture was added to a micro Bio-Spin™ chromatography columns (Bio-Rad #7326204) and the fraction containing the PETase of interest was collected into a new tube by centrifugation at 1,500 × g and 4 °C for 2 minutes.

Recombinant expression of PETases in *E. coli*

A pET-28a-derived plasmid containing a His6-tagged PETase gene was transformed into SHuffle® T7 Competent *E. coli* (New England Biolabs #C3026J) by following the manufacturer's instructions. The transformation was plated onto an LB Agar plate with 50 µg/mL kanamycin and incubated overnight at 37 °C. A single colony was used to inoculate 4 mL of LB medium with 50 µg/mL kanamycin in a 14-mL round-bottom test tube. The resulting seed culture was incubated at 37 °C and 250 rpm overnight.

The following day, 500 µL of the seed culture were used to inoculate 50 mL of LB medium with 50 µg/mL kanamycin. The resulting culture was incubated at 37 °C and 250 rpm until OD at 600 nm reached 0.6 - 0.8. At that point, expression of the PETase was induced by addition of Isopropyl β-D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) to a final concentration 0.5 mM and incubation at 25 °C and 250 rpm for 18 hours.

Cells with expressed PETase were harvested the following day by centrifugation in a 50-mL conical tube at 4,000 × g for 20 minutes. After discarding the supernatant, the resulting cell pellet was immediately used in the lysis protocol or stored at -80 °C until needed.

Lysis protocol for purification of recombinant PETases

The cell pellet was resuspended in the equilibration buffer (10 mM imidazole in 40 mM Tris buffer pH8) at a ratio of 4.5 mL per 1 g of cells. Once cells were fully resuspended, 500 µL/g of BugBuster® 10X protein extraction reagent (Millipore #70921) was added. The sample was incubated in ice for 15 minutes, mixing gently every few minutes. The resulting cell lysate was clarified by centrifugation at 20,000 × g and 4 °C for 20 minutes. The supernatant was transferred to a 15-mL conical tube and used for the purification by affinity chromatography step.

Purification of recombinant PETases via Ni-NTA affinity chromatography

Purification was carried out using HisPur™ Ni-NTA Spin Columns (ThermoScientific #8822) and an adapted version of the manufacturer's instructions. All centrifugation steps were carried out at 800 × g and 4 °C for 1 minute. Buffers and samples were kept in ice or at 4 °C. The Ni-NTA resin was equilibrated by incubating it with 2 column volumes (CVs) of the equilibration buffer for 5 - 10 minutes. The equilibration buffer was removed by centrifugation and discarded.

The equilibrated resin was resuspended in the clarified lysate and incubated in ice with light rocking for 1 hour. This step improves binding efficiency of the recombinant protein to the Ni-NTA resin. After incubation, the unbound components were removed by centrifugation. The resin column was washed by addition of 3 CVs of the wash buffer (30 mM imidazole in 40 mM Tris buffer pH 8) followed by centrifugation to discard the flowthrough. This step was repeated for a total of six wash cycles. The Ni-NTA column was transferred to a new collection tube, and the protein was eluted with a total of 7.5 CVs of the elution buffer (300 mM imidazole in 40 mM Tris buffer pH 8).

The excess imidazole in the resulting fraction was removed by buffer-exchange into the storage buffer (40 mM Tris buffer pH 8) using a molecular weight cutoff filter. Three cycles of 10-fold concentration/10-fold dilution in a fresh storage buffer were used. Absorbance at 280 nm was used to quantify the amount of purified protein and SDS-PAGE was used to determine purity. Aliquots of the purified PETase were flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C until needed.

PETase activity on fluorescent PET particles

PETase activity was tested on PET particles engulfing fluorescein dibenzoate (FDBz) that were prepared in-house. Enzymatic degradation of PET polymers through activity of PETases result in increased release of FDBz, which is also a substrate for PETases, resulting in the fluorescent product fluorescein. Thus, PETase activity can be followed by measuring the fluorescence of fluorescein after incubation of the enzyme with the PET particles. Enzymatic activity was measured at 25 °C, 55 °C, and 65 °C.

Reactions at 25 °C were set up in a microtiter 96-well plate with 100 µL/well of 5 µM recombinant PETase, 10% v/v PET/FDBz particles suspension, and 50 mM glycine-NaOH buffer pH 9 and incubated for 20 hours. Reactions at 55 °C and 65 °C were set up in microtiter 96-well plates with 100 µL/well of 1 µM recombinant PETase, 10% v/v PET/FDBz particles suspension, and 50 mM glycine-NaOH buffer pH 9 and incubated for 4 hours. After incubation, the fluorescence of fluorescein was measured in a plate reader, using 488 nm and 523 nm for the excitation and emission wavelengths, respectively. Activity via fluorescence assay was calculated as the fluorescence units per gram of protein and second (RFU / (g * sec)).

To correlate the fluorescence measurement to actual PET degradation, the samples were also analyzed via LCMS in order to detect the small molecule products Bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid (BHET), Mono-(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid (MHET), and terephthalic acid (TPA). For this purpose, reactions were quenched immediately after fluorescence measurement by addition of 100 µL 100% methanol, incubation at room temperature for 5 minutes, and centrifugation at 20,000 × g. The clarified supernatants were then submitted for LCMS analysis, with the small molecule products being quantified against external calibration curves. Activity via LCMS was calculated as the nmoles of all three products per gram of protein and second (nmol / (g * sec)).

PETase activity on PET film and powder

The activity of recombinant PETases was tested on two different PET substrates: PET film (Goodfellow #ES30-FM-000145) and PET powder (Goodfellow #ES30-PD-000132). These reactions were performed at 25 °C, 55 °C, and 65 °C.

Reactions at 25 °C were set up in a microtiter 96-well plate with 100 µL/well of 5 µM recombinant PETase, 29 mg/mL PET substrate, and 50 mM glycine-NaOH buffer pH 9 and incubated for 20 hours. Reactions at 55 °C and 65 °C were set up in microtiter 96-well plates with 100 µL/well of 1 µM recombinant PETase, 29 mg/mL PET substrate, and 50 mM glycine-NaOH buffer pH 9 and incubated for 4 hours. After incubation, reactions were quenched by addition of 100 µL 100%

methanol, incubation at room temperature for 5 minutes, and centrifugation at $20,000 \times g$. The clarified supernatants were then submitted for LCMS analysis, with the small molecule products BHET, MHET, and TPA being quantified against external calibration curves. Activity via LCMS was calculated as the nmoles of all three products per gram of protein and second ($\text{nmol} / (\text{g} \cdot \text{sec})$).

Preparation of Agarose Beads

Agarose (Sigma-Aldrich) was used as the unmodified matrix. Agarose (1 g) was dissolved in 25 mL of IDT buffer by heating until fully melted, split into two 50 mL Falcon tubes, and allowed to gel on ice for 30 min. The gels were washed as described above and resuspended in 20 mL of IDT buffer per tube to obtain a final concentration of 1.5% (w/v). The agarose was aliquoted into 1 mL volumes in 1.5 mL tubes and stored at 4°C until use. Agarose beads were generated by combining Benzylguanine (BG)-modified agarose, primer-modified agarose, and unmodified agarose in a ratio of 500 μL , 100 μL , and 400 μL , respectively, per 1 mL of precursor solution. Prior to mixing, all agarose stocks were melted at 95°C in a pre-heated thermoblock, with exposure of primer-modified agarose limited to 5–10 min to prevent degradation. The molten agarose solutions were mixed thoroughly, filtered while hot through a 0.22 μm or 0.45 μm filter, and loaded into a syringe maintained at approximately 42°C along with the associated tubing. Droplets were generated using a PDMS-based microfluidic device fabricated by standard soft lithography methods, with channel dimensions of approximately $35 \mu\text{m} \times 35 \mu\text{m} \times 25 \mu\text{m}$ and a height of 35 μm , using 2% (w/w) RAN surfactant in HFE-7500 oil as the continuous phase. Flow rates were set to 1000 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for the oil phase and 500 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ for the agarose phase, yielding droplets with an average diameter of $\sim 41 \mu\text{m}$. Droplets were collected in 15 mL Falcon tubes on ice and incubated for an additional 30–60 min to allow complete gelation. The emulsion was broken by removal of excess oil followed by addition of perfluoro-1-octanol (PFO), vortexing, and centrifugation. The resulting beads were washed five times with 10 mL of $0.1\times$ TBS buffer, centrifuging at $4000 \times g$ for 1 min at 4°C between washes, and stored at 4°C in $0.1\times$ TBS buffer.

PCR on Beads

PCR amplification on beads was performed using bead-immobilized forward primers, requiring only the addition of linear DNA template, reverse primer, and PCR master mix. Prior to PCR setup, beads were pelleted in 1.5 mL tubes by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 2 min and the storage buffer was removed. For each 100 μL of packed beads, 100 μL of HotStart Q5 $2\times$ Master Mix (New England Biolabs) was added along with reverse primer at a final concentration of $1 \mu\text{M}$ and an appropriate amount of linear DNA template (calculated based on a total reaction volume of 200 μL). Primer stocks were added directly without prior dilution to minimize added volume. The mixture was vortexed for 10 s, incubated on ice for 5 min, centrifuged, and $\sim 85\%$ of the supernatant was removed. To generate emulsions, 200 μL of Bio-Rad Droplet Generation Oil for EvaGreen was added, followed by vortexing for 1 min with intermittent manual agitation. The mixture was transferred to a 15 mL Falcon tube, and an additional 200 μL of oil was used to rinse the original tube and combined with the sample. Emulsification was continued by vortexing for 10 min with periodic agitation (≥ 3000 rpm), ensuring that each droplet contained a single bead as confirmed by microscopy. For larger beads ($>45 \mu\text{m}$), either Bio-Rad oil or 2% (w/w) RAN surfactant in HFE oil was used. The emulsion was briefly centrifuged (10 s at $400 \times g$), aliquoted into PCR tubes or plates ($\leq 80 \mu\text{L}$ per tube), and overlaid with mineral oil to prevent evaporation.

and droplet coalescence. PCR was performed using the following cycling conditions: initial denaturation at 98 °C for 30 s; 45 cycles of 98 °C for 30 s, 64 °C for 2.5 min, and 72 °C for 3 min; followed by a final extension at 72 °C for 10 min and a 4 °C hold. The annealing temperature was set 2 °C below the recommended value for Q5 polymerase. After amplification, samples were incubated at 4 °C for 30 min to allow agarose re-solidification. Emulsions were then broken by combining samples, removing mineral oil, and adding 200 µL perfluoro-1-octanol (PFO), followed by vortexing and centrifugation. The aqueous phase was washed with 1 mL of 0.1× TBS buffer, vortexed, and centrifuged, and residual oil was carefully removed. The beads were transferred to a fresh tube, avoiding carryover of the oil phase, and washed repeatedly (at least five times) with 1 mL of 0.1× TBS buffer until no visible PFO remained. Finally, beads were resuspended in 300 µL of 0.1× TBS buffer and passed through a 70 µm cell strainer prior to downstream use.

Cell-Free Expression on Beads

Following PCR and filtration, beads were pelleted by centrifugation and all residual liquid was removed. For each 100 µL of beads, 100 µL of NEBExpress synthesis buffer, 48 µL of S30 extract, and 4 µL of RNase inhibitor were added. The mixture was vortexed for 1 min, incubated on ice for 5 min, centrifuged, and approximately 85% of the supernatant was removed. Subsequently, 4 µL of T7 RNA polymerase was added and the sample was vortexed for 5 min. Emulsification was performed by adding 2% (w/w) RAN surfactant in HFE oil and vortexing as described above. The emulsion was transferred to a 15 mL tube, overlaid with mineral oil to fully cover the liquid phase, and incubated at room temperature for 24 h. Incubation at elevated temperatures was avoided to prevent loss of DNA from the agarose matrix, and shorter incubation times were not used due to reduced protein yield associated with the slow kinetics of the BG-SNAP reaction. Upon completion, cell-free expression beads were released from the droplets by PFO and washed five times with 0.1× TBS buffer.

Bead re-encapsulation

Beads displaying both DNA and protein variants (single variant per bead) were re-emulsified on a microfluidic coencapsulation device with 10% v/v PET/FDBz particles suspension, and 50 mM glycine-NaOH buffer pH 9 and incubated for 24 hours at room temperature or 55 °C. Upon completed incubation droplets were reinjected into a 70µm sorting microfluidic device by Atrandi Styx droplet sorter.

Droplet sorting

Following incubation, droplets were reinjected into a 70 µm microfluidic sorting device (Atrandi Styx droplet sorter) using 0.1% (w/w) RAN surfactant in HFE-7500 oil as the spacing phase. Droplets were analyzed based on green fluorescence intensity and signal duration, and sorting gates were defined using scatter plots of fluorescence intensity versus droplet duration to collect droplets in various brackets by the overall signal intensity. Sorted droplets (approximately 1000 drops per bin) were collected into 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes for downstream processing.

DNA Recovery

During sorting, droplets were collected into 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes and centrifuged at $14,000 \times g$ for 5 min, followed by rotation of the tubes and an additional centrifugation step under the same conditions to ensure complete phase separation. Subsequently, 25 μL of deionized water was added to each tube, and samples were frozen for at least 2 h to facilitate bead demulsification. Samples were then thawed and the aqueous phase was carefully transferred to a 384-well plate and centrifuged to pellet residual beads. Bead presence was verified by brightfield microscopy, after which the supernatant containing released DNA was transferred to PCR tubes for amplification. PCR reactions (50 μL total volume) were prepared using 25 μL of 2 \times Q5 Hot Start Master Mix (New England Biolabs), 0.5 μL each of 50 μM primers MD50 and MD51, 20 μL of recovered supernatant, and 4 μL of nuclease-free water. Amplification was performed using the following cycling conditions: initial denaturation at 98 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min; 30 cycles of 98 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 s and 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 41 s; followed by a final extension at 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min and a hold at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

A. Cell-free PETase expression purification

B. End-point UV-vis assay

C.

D.

F.

F.

H.

Figure 1. Platform 1: Cell-free expression and PET film degradation assay

A-B. Schematics of Cell-free expression and UV PET film degradation assay;

C. Quantification of soluble expression from cell-free protein synthesis crude extracts **D-G.**

End-point activity of 20 reference PETases using ΔA_{260} after 24 hours of reaction; **H.** MHET product equivalents after 37 hours of reaction

A. PETase expression, purification, and quantitation

B. PETase activity assay using rapid-fire mass spectrometry

C.

D.

E.

Figure 2. Platform 2: *E. coli* Expression and RFMS assay

A-B. Schematics of *E. coli*-based expression and RFMS activity assay;

C. Expression assay using A660 reagent after Ni-NTA affinity purification ; **D.** Development of RFMS activity assay under low and high pH condition using ten highly pure reference PETases PETases; **E.** Pilot-scale RFMS activity assay of 20 reference PETases

A. Droplet microfluidic expression assay

B. Droplet microfluidic PETase assay

C.

D.

E.

Figure 3. Microfluidic based cell-free expression and activity assay

A-B. Schematics of microfluidic droplet based cell-free expression and activity assay ;

C. Correlation between expression estimated based on relative NGS readcount in the microfluidic assay and LTP Qubit quantitation of each expressed PETase using CFPS. **D.** Correlation between expression estimated based on relative NGS readcount in the microfluidic assay and LTP specific activity measured using LCMS at 25 °C, and **E.** at 55 °C.

Figure S1. Time course of UV-based PET hydrolysis assay taken based on ΔA_{260}

A. Cell-free blank; **B.** FastPETase_new (Adaptyv's positive control); **C.** LCC PETase; **D.** IsPETase; **E.** Mipa PETase; **F.** Kubu PETase; **G.** Cut190; **H.** CaPETase; **I.** WP020639922.1; **J.** WP_117215036.1 **K.** SM14Est; **L.** WP083947829.1; **M.** PC5; **N.** Est2; **O.** WP_077759821.1 **P.** LCC PETase ICCG; **Q.** Mipa PETase M19 **R.** KubuPETase M12; **S.** FAST PETase; **T.** CaPETase M9; **U.** HotPETase; **V.** dMipa PETase (-lve ctrl); **W.** ecDHFR.

A

B.

37°C • pH 9

D.

Figure S2. UV end-point based activity for most active PETases

A. 37 °C pH 5.5, **B.** 37 °C pH 9.0, **C.** 60 °C pH 5.5, **D.** 60 °C pH 9.0 for seven of the most active PETase measured after diluting the reaction mixtures

Figure S3. Final OD of induced *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) culture of 20 reference PETases (N=9). Error bars represent standard deviations

Figure S4. Distribution of WT (parent and mutants) in plasmid library, amplified linear library, high and medium bin for microfluidic based activity assay on CaPETase SSVL library performed at 55 °C

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Conflict of Interest Statement

Daniel Nakhaee-Zadeh, Odeta Bondarevaite, and Artem Kononenko are employees of Adaptyv Biosystems and hold equity in the company.

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